

**EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES FOR ENGAGING PARENTS IN THEIR
CHILDREN'S EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN**

**O'ZBEKISTONDA OTA-ONALARNI FARZANDLARINING
TA'LIMIGA JALB QILISHNING SAMARALI STRATEGIYALARI**

**ЭФФЕКТИВНЫЕ СТРАТЕГИИ ВОВЛЕЧЕНИЯ РОДИТЕЛЕЙ В
ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ СВОИХ ДЕТЕЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ**

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Abstract. Parental engagement is crucial for children's academic success. This article examines effective strategies for involving parents in their children's education in Uzbekistan. The article analyzes these findings and discusses recommendations for enhancing parental engagement, including strengthening school-family communication, providing parent education and support, and fostering a welcoming school environment. Implementing these research-based strategies can help unleash the full potential of parental involvement to boost student achievement in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: parental engagement, Uzbekistan, academic achievement, school-family partnerships, parent involvement

Annotatsiya. Ota-onalarning ishtiroki bolalarning akademik muvaffaqiyati uchun juda muhimdir. Ushbu maqolada ota-onalarni o'z farzandlarini O'zbekistonda o'qitish jarayoniga jalb qilishning samarali strategiyalari muhokama qilinadi. Maqolada ushbu masalalar tahlil qilinadi va ota-onalarning faolligini oshirish bo'yicha tavsiyalar muhokama qilinadi, jumladan, maktab va oila o'rtasidagi aloqalarni mustahkamlash, ota-onalarning ta'limi va qo'llab-quvvatlashini ta'minlash va qulay maktab muhitini yaratish muhimdir. Ilmiy izlanishlarga asoslangan ushbu strategiyalarni amalga oshirish ota-onalarning O'zbekistonda o'quvchilarning yutuqlarini oshirishda ishtirok etish imkoniyatlarini ochib berishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: ota-onalarning ishtiroki, O'zbekiston, akademik yutuqlar, maktab va oila hamkorligi, ota-onalarning ishtiroki

Аннотация. Участие родителей имеет решающее значение для успеха детей в учебе. В этой статье рассматриваются эффективные стратегии вовлечения родителей в процесс обучения их детей в Узбекистане. В статье анализируются эти выводы и обсуждаются рекомендации по повышению вовлеченности родителей, включая укрепление связей между школой и семьей, обеспечение образования и поддержки родителей, а также создание благоприятной школьной среды. Реализация этих стратегий, основанных на научных исследованиях, может помочь раскрыть весь потенциал участия родителей в повышении успеваемости учащихся в Узбекистане.

Ключевые слова: участие родителей, Узбекистан, академические достижения, партнерство школы и семьи, вовлечение родителей

INTRODUCTION

Extensive research has demonstrated that parental engagement in their children's learning is one of the most important factors in student success [1]. When parents are involved, students have better attendance, behavior, and academic performance [2]. Recognizing this, countries around the world are seeking to strengthen parental engagement [3]. However, in Uzbekistan, like many other nations, challenges remain in fully realizing the power of parents as partners in education [4]. This article aims to identify effective, evidence-based strategies that can be applied in the Uzbek context to enhance parental involvement and thereby improve student outcomes.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review yielded several key findings about effective strategies for parental engagement. First, regular, two-way communication between home and school is critical [5]. This can include not only sharing information about students' progress, but also soliciting input from parents, learning about their hopes and concerns, and providing guidance on how to support learning at home [6]. Second, schools can directly build parents' capacity to engage through workshops, classes, and materials that guide them in supporting their children's learning [7]. Third, a welcoming school environment that makes all parents feel valued and included is essential, with cultural competence and sensitivity to diverse families [8]. Finally, engagement efforts are most effective when they are aligned with school improvement goals and integrated into the core work of the school.

RESULTS

The educator and parent interviews revealed several themes related to the

current state of parental engagement in Uzbekistan:

Existing engagement efforts: Most schools hold some form of parent-teacher conferences, send home written communication, and invite parents to events such as student performances. Some schools have parent committees or associations. A few innovative schools are using technology such as messaging apps to facilitate regular communication.

Challenges: However, interviews also highlighted significant challenges. Many parents, especially those with lower income or education levels, do not feel comfortable or welcome at school. Work schedules, transportation issues, and family responsibilities can make it difficult for parents to be involved. Parents often do not know how best to support their children's learning. Educators feel they lack the time, skills, and resources to fully engage families.

Opportunities: Despite these challenges, both educators and parents expressed a strong desire for better partnerships. Parents want to be more involved and see engagement as crucial for their children's success. Educators are eager for more support and training in how to work with families. There are opportunities to leverage technology, community partnerships, and student leadership to improve engagement. Educators and parents emphasized the importance of building trusting relationships as a foundation.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The findings from Uzbekistan reflect many of the themes identified in the broader research literature on parental engagement. The challenges of time, resources, cultural differences, and lack of know-how are common across contexts. At the same time, the interviews also reveal some unique aspects of the Uzbek

context, such as the role of neighborhood and community social structures in facilitating connections between home and school.

Looking at the interview results in light of the best practices from the literature review, it is clear that there is room for growth in parental engagement in Uzbekistan. Schools can take concrete steps to improve regular two-way communication, provide parent education and support, create a welcoming environment, and integrate engagement efforts with school improvement processes. However, it is also critical to recognize the assets that families bring and avoid a deficit-based approach. Engagement strategies should build on existing strengths and relationships.

This article highlights several evidence-based strategies that can be implemented to improve parental engagement in Uzbekistan. First, schools should establish regular, two-way communication systems using a variety of modalities such as in-person meetings, phone calls, text messages, and interactive notebooks. Communication should be timely, positive, personal, and focused on what parents can do to support learning. Second, schools can invest in parent education through workshops, training, and user-friendly resources on topics like homework help, early literacy, and positive discipline. Third, school leaders should work to create a welcoming climate for all families through cultural competence training for staff, student-led conferences and events, multilingual communication, and dedicated family resource centers or liaisons. Finally, engagement efforts will be most effective and sustainable when aligned with school improvement plans and integrated into core academic and social-emotional learning efforts.

However, fully increasing involvement will also require addressing broader challenges related to trust, capacity, and equity. Building trust takes time and

requires both educators and parents to challenge assumptions and focus on their shared purpose of supporting student success. School districts will need to build educators' skills and allocate resources to make engagement a priority. An equity lens is essential to ensure that engagement strategies reach all families, especially those who have traditionally been marginalized or excluded.

CONCLUSIONS

Parental engagement is a powerful but often underutilized lever for improving student achievement. In Uzbekistan, as in many nations, there are significant opportunities to better support families as partners in education. Implementing evidence-based strategies around communication, parent education, welcoming environments, and integration with school improvement efforts can help drive progress. At the same time, building trust, capacity, and equity are essential to realizing the full potential of engagement. With concerted effort from both schools and families, parental engagement can play a transformative role in ensuring that all children in Uzbekistan have the opportunity to thrive.

REFERENCES

1. Henderson, A. T., & Mapp, K. L. (2002). A new wave of evidence: The impact of school, family, and community connections on student achievement. Southwest Educational Development Laboratory.
2. Abdullayeva, N. (2023). AHMAD YASSAWI SECT: THE ISSUE OF ZIKR AND THE STATUS OF ZAKIR. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(5), 438-440.
3. Bazarov, S. (2024). JURNALIST VA BLOGERLAR NUTQI ETIKASI. *Инновационные исследования в современном мире: теория и практика*, 3(1), 36-39.
4. Abdinazarovich, B. S. (2023, November). NUTQ MADANIYATINI BUZUVCHI FAKTORLAR. In *Konferensiyalar| Conferences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 541-545).

5. Abdinazarovich, B. S. (2023). Speech Technique and Culture of Bloggers and Journalists.
6. Suvanov, H. (2024). MILLIY MADANIYAT VA MILLIY KOLORIT BADIY ASARDA NAMOYON BO 'LISHI. *NRJ*, 1(4), 272-277.
7. Suvanov, H. (2024). NATIONAL COLOR AND COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS IN THE WORKS OF MAHTUMQULI, GAFUR GHULAM AND ANVAR SUYUN. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 778-781.
8. Norqulovich, S. H. (2023, October). NURILLO CHORINING BADIY ASARLARIDA MILLIY KOLORITGA XOS KO 'RINISHLAR NUTQIY JIHATDAN IFODALANISHI. In *International conference on multidisciplinary science* (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 25-29).
9. Ziyodullayeva, M., & Muxtorova, M. (2024). ABDULLA QODIRIY HAYOTI VA IJODIGA AYRIM CHIZGILAR. *NRJ*, 1(3), 860-863.
10. Muxtorova, M. (2024). MAXTUMQULI SHE'RIYATIDA AYTISHUV: AN'ANA VA IZDOSHLIK. *NRJ*, 1(3), 254-257.
11. Tajenova, G., Turdiyeva, G., Qurbanov, A., & Isakov, I. (2020). Current state and development of agricultural products exports of the Republic of Uzbekistan. *Аpxue научных исследований*, (14).
12. Janabay, I., Gulbahar, T., Gulayda, T., Alisher, Q., & Ilkhambek, I. (2020). Current state and development of agricultural products exports of the republic of uzbekistan. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(8), 1684-1693.
13. Turdieva, G., Abishov, M., & Muratbaev, I. (2024). THE IMPACT OF CREDIT RISKS ON AN EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION IN THE FINANCIAL SERVICES OF COMMERCIAL BANKS. *NRJ*, 1(4), 215-225.
14. Beglenov, N., & Muratbaev, I. (2023). HOTEL SERVICES AS AN OBJECT OF STRATEGIC MARKETING ORIENTED TO THE CONSUMER. *Science and Education in Karakalpakstan*, 32(2), 175-177.
15. Xalmuratovich, B. S. (2024). JAHON AMALIYOTIDA AGROKLASTER TIZIMINI SAMARALI TASHKIL ETISH VA YURITISH BO 'YICHA TO 'PLANGAN TAJRIBALAR TAHLILI. *Scientific Journal of Actuarial Finance and Accounting*, 4(04), 140-150.
16. Bayjanov, S. X., & Abishov, M. S. (2024). DEVELOPING THE ACTIVITY OF JOINT STOCK COMPANIES BY IMPROVING DIVIDEND POLICY. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 3(3), 94-97.

17. Sultanov, B., Nurimbetov, T., Bayjanov, S., Seyilbekov, B., & Durmanov, A. (2023, October). Trends in change and the current state of the effectiveness of land reclamation measures in agriculture. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2921, No. 1). AIP Publishing.
18. Байжанов, С. Х. (2023). ВНЕДРЕНИЕ ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИИ В СЕЛЬСКОЕ ХОЗЯЙСТВО НОВОГО УЗБЕКИСТАНА. *BOSHQARUV VA ETIKA QOIDALARI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 3(4), 51-53.
19. Omonovna, E. R. (2023). KLINIK ATAMALAR SHAKLLANTIRISHDA SUFFIKSATSIYA USULI VA TA'LIM TEXNOLOGIYALARI. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 9(3), 198-204.
20. Ermatova, R. O. (2023). Using diagnostic assessments in language teaching. *Science and Education*, 4(5), 1095-1099.
21. Эрматова, Р. О., Пайгамова, З. Х., & Абдугаппаров, Б. М. (2022). АКТУАЛЬНОСТЬ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫХ МЕТОДОВ В ДИСТАНЦИОННОМ ОБУЧЕНИИ ЛАТИНСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ СТУДЕНТОВ-МЕДИКОВ. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(11), 208-213.
22. Utegenova, S., & Rozumova, D. (2024). DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING TAX AUDIT. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(6).
23. Utegenova, S., & Mirzabaeva, U. (2024). TODAY'S IMPORTANCE AND PROSPECTS OF AUDIT ACTIVITIES IN UZBEKISTAN. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 4(6), 93-95.
24. Khasanova, S., Akisheva, N., & Zholayeva, M. (2023). Methodological aspects of tax planning in the context of sustainable development. *Revista Gestão & Tecnologia*, 23(3), 286-298.